

Thermal Neutron Scattering Law Evaluation for Uranium-Molybdenum Alloy Fuels – Applications for Reactor Design and Criticality Safety

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ABSTRACT

Uranium-Molybdenum (U-Mo) alloy fuels have been heavily researched for decades in the effort to downgrade high enriched reactors to low enriched nuclear reactor fuels while maintaining high fissile densities. These alloys possess beneficial transformation kinetics with an optimal cubic γ -phase, which remains metastable at room temperature. This γ -phase uranium is stabilized via alloying with a transition metal like Mo and is prevented from decomposing while in a reactor environment by fission-induced irradiation impacts [1]. The amount of alloying required to stabilize the desired γ -U phase for reactor applications depends on both material and neutronic properties and is widely accepted to be between 7% and 10% Mo by weight. To fully understand the impact of this type of fuel alloying on both the performance and criticality safety of nuclear reactors, high-fidelity thermal neutron scattering data is required. Thermal neutron scattering cross sections have been calculated using *ab initio* techniques. These cross sections, applied in a reactor environment, describe the behavior of crucial thermal neutrons and the thermal neutron energy spectrum of the system [2]. In this work, thermal neutron scattering data for the tetragonal γ' phase of the U-Mo fuel alloy are calculated for various ²³⁵U enrichments. This evaluation was prepared with the aim of submitting to the ENDF/B-IX database and can be used directly in Monte Carlo simulations for reactor design and criticality safety calculations. The methods described in this paper will inform the future generation of thermal neutron scattering data for other U-Mo fuels with varying amounts of alloying.

Keywords: U-Mo Fuel, Thermal Neutron Scattering, Criticality Safety, RERTR

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1978, the United States Department of Energy (DOE) launched the Reduced Enrichment for Research and Test Reactors (RERTR) program with the goal of developing technology to allow for the reduction of uranium enrichment in both existing and future research and test reactors. A major goal of this program has been the development of advanced low-enriched uranium (LEU) fuels, where the maximizing of uranium density can serve to offset the decrease in fissile mass resulting from reduced enrichment. By 1987, U₃Si₂-Al dispersion fuel – uranium silicide homogeneously dispersed in aluminum – had emerged as the most promising advanced LEU fuel due to its high uranium density [3]. While this was later pushed even higher due to advancements in the fabrication process, the uranium content was still insufficient in offsetting the impact of lower enrichment in some high-flux research reactors. This deficiency has led to substantial research into uranium-molybdenum (U-Mo) alloy fuel, which has been the focus of worldwide advanced LEU fuel development since 1996 [1].

U-Mo alloy fuel was originally studied in the 1960's for use as fast reactor fuel. While uranium metal generally exists in three phases – an orthorhombic α -phase, a tetragonal β -phase, and a body-centered cubic (BCC) γ -phase [4] – the high-temperature γ -phase alloy is preferred as a fuel material due to both its mechanical properties and its superior behavior under irradiation. This cubic γ -phase, if alloyed with certain transition metals, can be retained in its metastable state at room temperature after cooling.

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While many transition metals have been considered for this alloy, Mo provides the best combination of γ -phase stabilization and increased uranium density; alloys with Mo can reach a maximum solubility in γ -U of higher than 17 wt.% [5]. While the metastable γ -UMo alloy will undergo a eutectoid decomposition below $\sim 565^\circ\text{C}$ into the α - and γ' -phases, fission-induced irradiation damage serves to stabilize the desired γ -phase in a reactor environment [1,6].

The U-Mo fuel alloys of highest interest to the nuclear reactor community generally contain 7-10% Mo by weight – alloys with Mo content lower than 7% by weight do not retain the metastable γ -phase at room temperature after quenching, and alloys must remain below 12% to minimize parasitic neutron absorption due to the absorption cross section of Mo [1]. U-7wt%Mo dispersion fuel was chosen for use in the KiJang Research Reactor (KJRR) [7], and has also been recommended for use in other existing and proposed reactors around the world [8].

In the pursuit of developing data to aid in the design of such reactors, this work seeks to develop high-fidelity thermal neutron scattering cross sections for the γ' -phase of the U-Mo fuel alloy. While this U_2Mo phase (sometimes also called the δ - or ε -phase [4]) may not always be the target composition for reactor applications, the *ab initio* methods employed in this work will inform the development of thermal neutron scattering data for the higher-temperature γ -phase with 7-10% Mo content.

2. THERMAL NEUTRON SCATTERING THEORY

In a thermal reactor, fast neutrons born from fission lose energy via interactions with atomic media in a process called thermalization. This successive energy loss results in neutrons which exist in thermal equilibrium with their media – thermal neutrons – which are in the correct energy range to cause further fission reactions in the fissile fuel. The thermal neutron spectrum is vital to the neutron economy of a thermal reactor – without accurate thermal neutron scattering data, neither the fission reaction rate nor thermal neutron population can be fully understood. These values are necessary for the calculation of k_{eff} (via the six-factor formula), and therefore the thermal neutron scattering cross sections are of crucial importance to reactor design, operation, and criticality safety.

Thermal neutron scattering cross sections can be derived *ab initio* from quantum scattering theory. The result is an expression for the double-differential scattering cross section, which describes the likelihood of a thermal neutron of incident energy E scattering into a secondary energy dE' about E' through a solid angle $d\Omega$ about Ω . This quantity provides both secondary energy and angular distributions – quantities which are important to reactor modeling and criticality safety. The standard double-differential scattering cross section is shown in Equation (1) below, where T is the temperature of the scattering system; k_B is the Boltzmann constant; σ_{coh} and σ_{inc} are the bound coherent and incoherent atomic scattering cross sections, respectively; and $S(\alpha, \beta)$ is the thermal scattering law (TSL) of the scattering system [2,9].

$$\frac{d^2\sigma}{\partial\Omega\partial E'} = \frac{1}{4\pi k_B T} \sqrt{\frac{E'}{E}} [\sigma_{coh} S(\alpha, \beta) + \sigma_{inc} S_s(\alpha, \beta)] \quad (1)$$

2.1. Inelastic Neutron Scattering

The TSL, as can be seen from Equation (1), is the fundamental property which dictates the scattering of thermal neutrons. It describes the energy and momentum states of the scattering system which are available for the interaction with an incident neutron. In its most basic form, the TSL is the Fourier transform of the time-dependent pair correlation function $G(\mathbf{r}, t)$ of the scattering system [10]. It is therefore an inherent property of the material, and as a result so are thermal neutron scattering cross sections. The relationship between $S(\alpha, \beta)$ and $G(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is shown in Equation (2). Here, κ is the scattering vector, \mathbf{r} the position vector, ω frequency, and t time. For purposes of thermal neutron scattering theory, the TSL is represented as a function of the dimensionless momentum- and energy-transfer variables α and β , respectively shown in Equations (3) and (4). The additional variables in these definitions are the ratio of the scatterer mass (m) and neutron mass A , and the cosine of the scattering angle in the laboratory frame μ .

$$S(\alpha, \beta) = k_B T \cdot S(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \omega) = \frac{k_B T}{2\pi\hbar} \int G(\mathbf{r}, t) \exp\{i(\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t)\} d\mathbf{r} dt \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{\hbar^2 \boldsymbol{\kappa}^2}{2mk_B T} = \frac{E' + E - 2\mu\sqrt{EE'}}{Ak_B T} \quad (3)$$

$$\beta = -\frac{\hbar\omega}{k_B T} = \frac{E' - E}{k_B T} \quad (4)$$

The TSL $S(\alpha, \beta)$ can be further categorized into two components: the self-component $S_s(\alpha, \beta)$ which correlates an atom to itself, and the distinct-component $S_d(\alpha, \beta)$ which correlates an atom to other atoms in the system – the TSL is therefore comprised of both interference (coherent) terms and noninterference (incoherent) terms. Historically, the incoherent approximation is applied to the calculation of the TSL, whereby the coherent contributions are considered negligible and therefore $S_d(\alpha, \beta) = 0$. Furthermore, when a thermal neutron scatters inelastically within a material, it exchanges energy and momentum with the material lattice via the creation or annihilation of a phonon. If the forces in a system are assumed to be harmonic (the harmonic approximation), the TSL can be described as a summation of p -phonon interactions wherein a neutron scattering in the system will create or destroy p phonons. The inelastic double-differential cross section can be rewritten under both the incoherent and harmonic approximations as shown below in Equation (5). As a result of this dependence on the phonons in a material, the primary input required to calculate the TSL is the phonon density of states (DOS).

$$\left(\frac{d^2\sigma}{\partial\Omega\partial E'} \right)_{inelastic} = \frac{1}{4\pi k_B T} \sqrt{\frac{E'}{E}} [[\sigma_{coh} + \sigma_{inc}]] \sum_{p>0} S_s^p(\alpha, \beta) \quad (5)$$

2.2. Elastic Neutron Scattering

The elastic scattering of thermal neutrons can be either incoherent or coherent, with the likelihood of either corresponding to the magnitudes of the bound incoherent and coherent cross sections of the scattering atoms. Incoherent elastic scattering does not include interference effects – it corresponds to the zero-phonon term of the phonon expansion. Coherent elastic scattering is a phenomenon which results from the interference of neutron waves which scatter from successive planes of atoms in a crystalline structure. This type of scattering corresponds to diffraction in a material – as such, it is inherently dependent upon the crystalline structure and all constituent atoms.

The general form of the coherent elastic cross section is shown below in Equation (6), and can be related to the 0-order phonon term of the TSL (i.e., S^0) via correlation functions [10]. The variable N is number of atoms in the unit cell, v_0 is the volume of the unit cell, and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is a reciprocal lattice vector. The Dirac-delta function is the representation of Bragg's law in reciprocal space, and $|F(\boldsymbol{\kappa})|^2$ is the nuclear unit-cell structure factor. This, as defined in Equation (7), is a summation over all atoms d in the unit cell which includes their bound coherent scattering lengths \bar{b}_d , their position vector \mathbf{d} , and the Debye-Waller temperature factor W_d . This latter factor accounts for the thermal motion of atoms and leads to a reduction in the coherent elastic scattering cross section with increasing temperature. The calculation of the temperature factor is simplified by introducing the cubic approximation, which assumes that the forces in the crystal do not have strong directional dependence.

$$\left(\frac{d^2\sigma}{\partial\Omega} \right)_{coh\ el} = N \frac{(2\pi)^3}{v_0} \sum_{\boldsymbol{\tau}} \delta(\boldsymbol{\kappa} - \boldsymbol{\tau}) |F(\boldsymbol{\kappa})|^2 \quad (6)$$

$$|F(\boldsymbol{\kappa})|^2 = \sum_d \bar{b}_d e^{i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \mathbf{d}} e^{-W_d} \quad (7)$$

3. U-MO MATERIAL MODELING

The crystal structure of γ' -U₂Mo is body-centered tetragonal (BCT) with symmetry described by the $I4/mmm$ Hermann-Mauguin space group (#139). The U₂Mo unit cell contains two non-equivalent atom sites (i.e., sites not related by symmetry) – one site belongs to uranium and includes four atoms, and the other corresponds to molybdenum and includes two atoms. A density-functional theory (DFT) optimization of the structure was performed using the Vienna Ab Initio Simulation Program (VASP) [11-13]. While γ' -U₂Mo is known to be nonmagnetic and therefore spin-polarization and spin-orbit coupling were not considered [14], the model incorporates DFT+U to improve the description of the localized d - and f -orbital electrons of the uranium atoms. Hubbard U_{eff} values of 3 and 0 were used for U and Mo, respectively. The cell shape and atomic positions were allowed to change during the simulation, but the volume of the cell was fixed to combat the lattice distortion caused by the introduction of the DFT+U correction. The structure optimization informed a planewave cutoff of 400 eV and a 9x9x6 Monkhorst-Pack k -point mesh [15]. Results of the optimization were validated by comparing the structure to experimental lattice parameters (i.e., lengths of the crystalline unit cell), where good agreement is found as shown in Table I below.

Table I. Lattice parameter comparison.

	This Work	Experiment [16]	Percent Error
Lattice Parameter a (Å)	3.442	3.427	0.438
Lattice Parameter c (Å)	9.747	9.854	1.086

VASP and Phonopy [17-18] were used to calculate phonon dispersions and DOSs for the optimized U₂Mo structure by solving the dynamical matrix. Generation of the required Helmann-Feynman forces was achieved by applying several 0.01 Å displacements to a 3x3x2 supercell of 108 atoms. Due to the increased cell dimensions, the k -point mesh was reduced to 3x3x2.

The partial phonon DOSs were processed in the Full Law Analysis Scattering System Hub (*FLASSH*) [19] code to evaluate TSLs for both U and Mo in U₂Mo, which were printed according to ENDF-6 format [20]. The inelastic cross section was calculated under the incoherent, harmonic, and cubic approximations according to Equation (5) with a phonon-order of 300 to ensure convergence to the free-atom cross section at high energies. The coherent elastic cross section was also calculated for the compound using experimental lattice parameters and atomic positions [16,21]. Incoherent elastic contributions are considered negligible based on the relative magnitudes of the bound coherent and incoherent cross sections for both U and Mo [22].

To further support the development and application of U-Mo alloy fuels, the cross sections for γ' -U₂Mo were calculated for a variety of uranium enrichments. In addition to natural uranium, data was generated for the following enrichments of ²³⁵U : 5% (LEU), 10% (LEU+), 19.75% (high enriched low-assay uranium – HALEU), 93% (high enriched uranium – HEU), and 100% (pure ²³⁵U). To achieve this, the mass and cross sections of uranium used in the *FLASSH* calculations were varied. However, the same phonon DOS was used in all evaluations due to the small impact of the variation of uranium mass on the vibrational spectra [23]. While U-Mo alloy fuels may only be enriched up to HALEU levels, the higher enrichments are included for completeness. Natural molybdenum was used for all evaluations, and the cross sections were evaluated for a temperature grid of 293.6, 400, 500, 600, 700, and 800 K.

4. RESULTS

The calculated partial phonon DOS for both U and Mo in γ' -U₂Mo are shown below in Figure 1, where the distributions are normalized such that the area is unity. The low-energy acoustic regions for both components can be seen to follow the expected ω^2 Debye behavior. There are two distinct optical modes in the vibrational spectrum of Mo – the relative magnitudes of these modes follow are typical a lighter nuclide bound to a heavier nuclide, which results in higher vibrational frequencies. Conversely, the uranium atoms primarily oscillate in the acoustic range. It is important to note that, due to the mechanical instability of γ' -U₂Mo at very low temperatures, several negative phonon modes exist in the

phonon dispersion curves. This led to the DOS minimally extending into the negative energy range. While the existence of these nonphysical negative modes is not ideal, they were small and therefore excluded in the calculation of the TSL and cross sections in *FLASSH*.

Figure 1. Partial phonon DOS for U and Mo in U_2Mo

The TSL under the incoherent approximation, calculated using a phonon expansion order of 300, is evaluated individually for both U and Mo in γ' - U_2Mo using their respective partial phonon DOSs. Figure 2 and Figure 3 below highlight the TSL as a function of momentum transfer α (at select values of β) and energy transfer β (at select values of α), respectively. The fine structure of the DOS can be seen reflected in the latter at low values of α .

Figure 2. $S_s(\alpha, \beta)$ vs α for (a) U in U_2Mo and (b) Mo in U_2Mo at select β values

Figure 3. $S_s(\alpha, \beta)$ vs β for (a) U in U_2Mo and (b) Mo in U_2Mo for select values of α

Finally, the thermal neutron scattering cross sections for the γ' - U_2Mo compound are shown in Figure 4. While *FLASSH* generates the TSL and cross sections on a per-atom basis, the cross sections of the compound are created by stoichiometrically combining the data of the constituent elements. This plot highlights the inelastic and total cross sections at select temperatures and enrichments. There is a clear proportional impact on the inelastic cross section with higher enrichments due to the increasing total bound scattering cross section. The total compound scattering cross section appropriately asymptotes to the total free atom cross section at high energy values.

Figure 4. The inelastic scattering cross section of U_2Mo shown at selected temperatures and enrichments. The natural and high enriched total scattering cross sections for U_2Mo at 293.6 K are also shown.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents high-fidelity thermal neutron scattering data for the γ' -phase of U-Mo alloy fuel. The U₂Mo compound was modeled using *ab initio* methods to obtain accurate Hellmann-Feynman forces and ultimately the vibrational spectrum of the material in the form of the phonon DOS. Utilizing the *FLASSH* code [19] and this DOS, the TSL and subsequent thermal neutron scattering cross sections were calculated for both U and Mo in U₂Mo. The data was generated for a range of ²³⁵U enrichments to further support the development of U-Mo alloy fuels – LEU, LEU+, HALEU, HEU, and pure ²³⁵U. The results reported here will serve as a crucial tool for the design and criticality safety analysis of high-interest U-Mo alloy fuels in low-enrichment nuclear reactors. The TSLs and elastic cross sections will be submitted in ENDF-6 format for publication in the upcoming ENDF/B-IX database, and the details outlined in this paper will inform the future development of similar data for additional U-Mo alloy fuels.

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